

ADSORPTION OF MONO- AND POLYBASIC ACIDS BY SUGAR CHARCOAL.

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The adsorption of mono-, di- and tri-carboxy acids and bi-salts of dibasic acids by sugar charcoal activated at 800-850° has been studied. Adsorption of solutes, particularly monocarboxy acids, from solution by sugar charcoal follows the ordinary laws of adsorption and is mainly a surface phenomenon as $\log x$ and $\log C$ curves are straight lines.

While studying adsorption of polybasic acids and their acid salts curious adsorption curves of somewhat periodic nature were obtained. Although a considerable amount of work seems to have been done in this direction this fact escaped notice by the previous workers. Sabalitschka and Finger (Dissrtn. Berlin, 1927-28); T. Sabalitschka (*Pharm. Ztg.*, 1924, 72, 382), Nekrassov (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 136, 18, 379); Dubinin (*ibid.*, 1929, 140, 81; 1930, 150, 145; *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 62, 1829), Bruns (*Kolloid Z.*, 1931, 54, 33), Roychaudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 433), and others studied the adsorption of mono- and dibasic acids by sugar charcoal, and all the workers mentioned above obtained smooth curves, showing regularity in adsorption.

While monobasic acids, both aliphatic and aromatic, behaved normally, the adsorption curves obtained from organic and inorganic di- and tribasic acids were invariably somewhat of a periodic nature.

Adsorption curves obtained for the acid salts of dibasic acids also give curves which are similar to those obtained from acids themselves.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Sugar Charcoal.—Crystals of cane sugar were carbonised with strong sulphuric acid and repeatedly washed with boiling distilled water till free from acid. It was then dried, ground to fine powder and passed through 120 mesh sieve. It was finally heated in a muffle furnace at 800-850° for nearly an hour. After heating the charcoal was left in a well stoppered bottle out of contact with air. The sample of the charcoal thus prepared left 0.42% of residue on ignition.

Method of Analysis.—The adsorption experiments were carried out by weighing exactly 1 g. of the charcoal in clean, dry, glass bottles, similar in size to which 100 c.c. of the acid solution in freshly prepared distilled water were pipetted. The bottles were shaken for the same length of time and kept for about 18 hours, after which the amount of the solute was deter-

mined in the supernatant liquid by usual analytical methods. The original concentration (C_0) was the amount of the solute originally taken in bottles, that in equilibrium with the charcoal is represented by C_e . The amount of adsorption (x) was determined by differences. The experiments were repeated with every care.

Results for adsorption of various acids are recorded in Tables I and II, while that of bi-salts in Table III.

TABLE I.

Dibasic acids.

Adsorption by 1 g. of the charcoal from 100 c.c. of the aqueous solution of acids.

Acids.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	Log C_e .	Log x .
Oxalic	2.9782	1.9255	0.0527	0.4661	$\bar{2}.7217$
	2.8293	2.7554	0.0739	0.4401	$\bar{2}.8685$
	2.6804	2.6193	0.0611	0.4181	$\bar{2}.7657$
	2.5315	2.4832	0.0483	0.3950	$\bar{2}.6835$
	2.3825	2.3132	0.0693	0.3642	$\bar{2}.8409$
	2.2336	2.1771	0.0565	0.3379	$\bar{2}.7523$
	2.0847	2.0410	0.0437	0.3098	$\bar{2}.6409$
	1.9358	1.8710	0.0648	0.2720	$\bar{2}.8119$
	1.7869	1.7348	0.0521	0.2390	$\bar{2}.7171$
	1.6380	1.5988	0.0392	0.2032	$\bar{2}.5937$
Malonic	2.9782	2.8920	0.0862	0.4612	$\bar{2}.9354$
	2.8293	2.7516	0.0777	0.4395	$\bar{2}.8902$
	2.6804	2.5831	0.0973	0.4121	$\bar{2}.9880$
	2.5315	2.4573	0.0742	0.9904	$\bar{2}.8702$
	2.3825	2.3023	0.0802	0.3621	$\bar{2}.9044$
	2.2336	2.1620	0.0716	0.3349	$\bar{2}.8551$
	2.0847	2.0216	0.0631	0.3056	$\bar{2}.8003$
	1.9358	1.8671	0.0687	0.2711	$\bar{2}.8373$
	2.7869	1.7127	0.0742	0.2335	$\bar{2}.8706$
	1.6380	1.5727	0.0653	0.1955	$\bar{2}.8198$

TABLE I (contd.).

Acids.	C_0 .	C_e .	x_e .	$\text{Log } C_e$.	$\text{Log } x_e$.
Succinic	2.9782	2.8671	0.1111	0.4575	1.0457
	2.8293	2.7346	0.0947	0.4368	2.9762
	2.6804	2.5645	0.1159	0.4089	1.0638
	2.5315	1.4241	0.1104	0.3840	1.0427
	2.3825	2.2937	0.0888	0.3604	2.9486
	2.2336	2.1344	0.0992	0.3292	2.9967
	2.0847	1.9751	0.1096	0.2956	1.0402
	1.9358	1.8318	0.1040	0.2630	1.0172
	1.7869	1.6884	0.0985	0.2275	2.9936
	1.6380	1.5451	0.0929	0.1889	2.9682
Phthalic	1.3990	0.3798	0.0192	1.5789	2.2821
	0.3790	0.3608	0.0182	1.5573	2.2608
	0.3590	0.3411	0.0180	1.5329	2.2542
	0.3391	0.3178	0.0213	1.5022	2.3249
	0.3192	0.3001	0.0191	1.4772	2.2806
	0.2992	0.2767	0.0225	1.4419	2.3536
	0.2793	0.2661	0.0132	1.4251	2.1199
	0.2593	0.2426	0.0167	1.3889	2.2235
	0.2394	0.2204	0.0190	1.3432	2.2786

FIG. 1.

The results for the adsorption of di- and tri-carboxy acids are given in Tables I and II. It will be seen that the order of adsorption : succinic > malonic > oxalic shows that the adsorption increases with increase in molecular weight, *i.e.*, in favour of the Traube's rule for homologous series.

TABLE II.

Tribasic acids.

Adsorption by 1 g. of charcoal from 100 c.c. of aqueous solution of acids.

Acids.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	Log C_e .	Log x .
Citric	2.5540	2.5348	0.0190	0.4037	$\bar{2}.2788$
	2.4261	2.4034	0.0227	0.3807	$\bar{2}.3562$
	2.2984	2.2720	0.0264	0.3564	$\bar{2}.4219$
	2.1707	2.1405	0.0302	0.3305	$\bar{2}.4804$
	2.0430	2.0279	0.0151	0.3071	2.1801
	1.9153	1.8776	0.0378	0.2735	2.5769
	1.7877	1.7650	0.0227	0.2468	$\bar{2}.3553$
	1.6599	1.6335	0.0265	0.2131	$\bar{2}.4229$
	1.5323	1.5209	0.0114	0.1821	$\bar{2}.0562$
	1.4646	1.3895	0.0152	0.1429	$\bar{2}.1816$

TABLE III.

Bi-salts of dibasic acids.

Adsorption by 1 g. charcoal from 100 c.c. of aqueous solutions of salt.

Bi-salt.	C_0 .	C_e .	x .	Log C_e .	Log x .
Pot. hydrogen phthalate	2.2792	2.2579	0.0213	0.3537	$\bar{2}.3284$
	2.1652	2.1301	0.0351	0.3284	$\bar{2}.5858$
	2.0513	2.0021	0.0489	0.3014	$\bar{2}.6900$
	1.9373	1.9064	0.0309	0.2801	$\bar{2}.4903$
	1.8233	1.7893	0.0341	0.2527	$\bar{2}.5323$

TABLE III (contd.).

Bi-salt.	C_0	C_e	x	$\text{Log } C_e$	$\text{Log } x$
Sod. hydrogen succinate	1.4843	1.4306	0.0537	0.1554	2.7300
	1.4101	1.3702	0.0399	0.1367	2.6013
	1.3359	1.2991	0.0368	0.1138	2.5658
	1.2617	1.2224	0.0393	0.0871	2.5942
	1.1875	1.1552	0.0323	0.0626	2.5088
	1.1133	1.0746	0.0387	0.0311	2.5873
Sod. hydrogen oxalate	1.3775	1.3632	0.0143	0.1345	2.1545
	1.3086	1.3065	0.0021	0.1159	3.3304
	1.2397	1.2284	0.0114	0.0892	2.0558
	1.1709	1.1645	0.0064	0.0660	3.8062
	1.1020	1.0934	0.0086	0.0387	3.9340
	1.0331	1.0295	0.0036	0.0124	3.5587

The results for the adsorption of bi-salts of dicarboxy acids : phthalic, succinic and oxalic acids are given in Table III. From Figs. 1 and 2 the order of adsorption : sodium hydrogen succinate > sodium hydrogen oxalate shows that the adsorption increases with the increase in molecular weight, as in these acids.

FIG. 2.

DISCUSSION.

In the accompanying experiments, we have got irregular curves with polybasic acids, e.g., oxalic, malonic, succinic, phthalic, citric, and with

bi-salts of dibasic acids, *e.g.* sodium hydrogen oxalate, sodium hydrogen succinate, and potassium hydrogen phthalate. We had taken all the precautions to avoid contact with oxygen as far as possible. Even if it be granted that a slight oxidation was going on along with the adsorption there is no reason why the curve should be a zigzag one as has been observed. Moreover, chromic and phosphoric acids do not oxidise in which case also irregular curves have been obtained.

Adsorption of monocarboxy acids seems greater than that of dicarboxy acids both in aliphatic and aromatic series. In a homologous series it increases strongly and regularly as we ascend the series. The percentage of adsorption increases as the concentration decreases in monocarboxy acids.

The adsorption curves in case of dibasic, tribasic acids and those of bi-salts of dibasic acids are zigzag.

At present it is not possible for us to fix the cause of irregularities that have been observed. Further work is being done and it is hoped that some explanation might be forthcoming.

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